

UNIVERSITY
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Proteoform Peak Integration Facilitates DAR Estimation from Orbitrap Mass Spectra of Complex ADCs

**Konstantin O. Nagornov,¹ Natalia Gasilova,² Anton N. Kozhinov,¹ Pasi Virta,³
Patrik Holm,⁴ Laure Menin,² Victor J. Nesatyy,⁴ and Yury O. Tsybin¹**

¹ Spectroswiss, Lausanne, Switzerland

² Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland

³ Department of Chemistry, University of Turku, Turku, Finland

⁴ Protein and Antibody Engineering Unit, Orion Pharma, Turku, Finland

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Antibody-Oligonucleotide Conjugate (AOC)

Oligonucleotides – **selectively** arrest protein production by targeting specific genes

AOCs: Jain *et al.*, *J. Clin. Med.* 2021 Wagner *et al.*, *Bioconj. Chem.* 2019

Sample: a trastuzumab-oligonucleotide conjugate with ~7 kDa per payload (size & ionization)

Nagornov *et al.*, *Anal Chem*, 2021, 12930

Objective: To Estimate the Drug-to-Antibody Ratio

Drug-to-antibody ratio (**DAR**) is the average number of drugs conjugated to an antibody

trastuzumab conjugated
with oligonucleotides

SEC: size-exclusion chromatography

Native SEC
Q Exactive HF BioPharma
60k @ 200 m/z

unresolved proteoforms

- Sample preparation (deglycosylation)
- Data analysis algorithms

Approaches to Heterogeneity in Native MS
Prell et al., Chem. Rev., 2021

Addressing Mass Spectrum Complexity

resolution

Sample:
Intact AOC

Experiment:
Native conditions
SEC-Orbitrap
(Q Exactive HF)

Anal Chem, 2021, 12930

The AOC Sample Complexity

mAb glycoforms
(charge states)

+51

+51

G0/G0F
G0F/G0F
G0F/G1F
G1F/G1F
G1F/G2F

Deglycosylation?

+ cross-linkers
(4-8 cross linkers)

+51

modified

FTMSIMULATOR

Q Exactive HF
15k @ 200 m/z

WP051

JASMS 2020, 1927

The AOC Sample Complexity

←-----→

+51 - +54

+ payload (drugs)
(4-8 drugs, 1.2 kDa)

+51 - +54

+ modifications
(16, 32, 44, ... Da)

FTMSIMULATOR

Q Exactive HF
15k @ 200 m/z

WP051

JASMS 2020, 1927

Solution: Proteoform Peak Integration

R
resolution

Isotopes
(fine structure)

Isotopologues
(monoisotopic mass)

Proteoforms
(average mass)

**Integrated
Proteoforms**

From resolved
to **integrated**
proteoforms

R ↓

FTMS**SIMULATOR**

Q Exactive HF 30k
@ 200 m/z

How to Reduce Resolution to Integrate Proteoforms?

- directly via lower resolution mass spectra – limit of 15k @ m/z 200 (Q Exactive HF)
- via truncation of the **time-domain transients**, e.g., using an add-on DAQ system

time-domain
transient

$$R \sim T$$

Anal Chem, 2021, 12930

JASMS 2020, 257

JASMS 2021, 1224

QE schematics: www.planetorbitrap.com

Proteoform Peak Integration Workflow

Analysis of an Antibody-Crosslinker Conjugate

Native mode analysis of trastuzumab modified with cross-linkers

Sample separation with SEC (20 ug per infusion)

FTMS: a Q Exactive HF BioPharma. Settings: AGC 5e6, resolution 60k at m/z 200 (128 ms)

Analysis of an Antibody-Crosslinker Conjugate

mAb sample:
trastuzumab
(Herceptin)

cross-linkers:
NHS-PEG4-Azide
 $C_{11}H_{19}N_3O_5$
MW = 273.29 Da

Experiment:
Native conditions
SEC-Orbitrap
(Q Exactive HF)

Transients:
FTMS Booster
Peak-by-Peak

Analysis of an Intact AOC Sample: Full Elution Peak

resolution

Sample:
Intact AOC

Experiment:
Native conditions
SEC-Orbitrap
(Q Exactive HF)

Transients:
FTMS Booster
Peak-by-Peak

Analysis of an Intact AOC Sample: Sliding Window

Application of a sliding window approach to LC-MS analysis of AOCs

$$\text{DAR} = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^m (I_n \times n)}{\sum_{n=0}^m I_n}$$

Integrated approach

DARs: Integrated approach (5.22) vs. Sliding window approach (4.55)

Sliding window approach: ADC – Thermo PO72283; mAbs – *Eur J Pharm Biopharm* 2021 158: 83

What if the AOC sample complexity is reduced?

Analysis of an Intact AOC Sample: Sliding Window

Application of a sliding window approach to LC-MS analysis of AOCs

DARs: Integrated approach (5.22) vs. Sliding window approach (4.55)

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What if the AOC sample complexity is reduced?

Analysis of an Antibody Subunit-Drug Conjugate

resolution

AOC sample:
IdeS-derived
F(ab)₂ subunit of
trastuzumab
(~100 kDa) with
oligonucleotides
of ~7 kDa each

Experiment:
Native conditions
SEC-Orbitrap
(Q Exactive HF)

Transients:
FTMS Booster
Peak-by-Peak

Analysis of an Antibody Subunit-Drug Conjugate

Application of a sliding window approach to LC-MS analysis of ADCs

DAR estimate: Integrated approach (3.50) vs. Sliding window approach (3.57)

The revealed DARs are in line with the anticipated and simulated values

Conclusions

“resolved” proteoforms

integrated proteoforms

Anal Chem, 2021, 12930

- Proteoform peaks can be integrated by **significant** resolution reduction in Orbitrap FTMS
- **Proteoform integration shows utility for DAR analysis on complex ADC/AOC samples**
- **Sliding window** approach applied to ADC/AOC LC-MS data increases analysis accuracy
- Resolution reduction by user-controlled time-domain transient truncation is readily available
- Practical implementation: method automatization and optimization; comparison with TOF MS
- Other use cases in the analysis of heterogenous samples, different ADC/AOC complexity?

Resolution – Use with Caution! Sometimes Less is More.

Thank you!

WP051

ThP120

FTMS

Workshop

(Wednesday)

Spectroswiss

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